

electrode and platinum wire electrode as an auxiliary electrode. The characteristics were as follows: pre-electrolysis potential = -1.2 V vs SCE, potential range = ± 2.0 V, scan rate = 5 mV s⁻¹, pulse amplitude = 10 mV, sensitivity = 10 μ A/V, acquisition fast, pre-electrolysis time = 80 s, resting period = 100 s; surface area of working electrode = 0.42 cm²; on polarocord X-axis = 200 mV cm⁻¹, Y-axis = 200 mV cm⁻¹. Total volume of experimental solution was 100 ml, and deaeration was done with 99.9% pure nitrogen gas passed for 5 min. Polarograms for blank sets were also recorded.

Results and Discussion

Zinc(II) gave a well-defined polarographic reduction wave in sodium acetate (0.03 M) at pH = 4.30 ± 0.02 . The nature of the supporting electrolyte plays a significant role in stripping analysis. It was found that sodium acetate at pH = 4.30 is an ideal medium as it prevented hydrolysis by controlling pH and in case of simultaneous determination of Cu, Zn, Cd and Pb also provided good resolution between adjacent stripping peaks³. It was observed that peak height was proportional to the zinc taken. Calibration plots and standard addition method was found to be valid upto 0.30 μ g ml⁻¹. The results showed that the technique is sufficiently sensitive and produced highly satisfactory reproducibility.

The effect of presence of Cu, Cd, Pb and Fe could be tolerated upto 1 : 50 (Zn : Cu); 1 : 50 (Zn : Cd); 1 : 100 (Zn : Pb) and 1 : 250 (Zn : Fe) ratios and within the range Zn and the said metals have also been determined simultaneously. An advantage of the method is that iron is tolerated upto sufficiently large extent thereby permitting the determination in iron ores and in pyrites residues. In presence of 25-folds of Co and Ni, a decrease in peak current (I_p) was observed.

Determination of Zn^{II} in natural water samples: The water samples were collected from the Sagar lake (Sagar town of Madhya Pradesh). Any suspended impurities were removed by filtration and the filtrate was treated with a few drops of concentrated HNO₃. The solution was evaporated to dryness and the volume was made upto 10 ml with triple-distilled water. Suitable aliquots of water sample were taken in the cell along with sodium acetate solution (10 ml of 0.3 M) and the volume was made upto 100 ml with triple-distilled water and polarograms were recorded, the same samples were analysed using atomic absorption spectrometric method (Table 1). The recovery experiments were performed with the addition of known quantities of Zn^{II} in the natural water samples and the recovery was found to be 99.85%.

Determination of Zn^{II} in human blood: Venous blood sample (5.0 ml) of healthy as well as diseased persons were collected separately. After adding sodium citrate (3.5 mg) to it as anticoagulant the sample was swirled for 1 min. It was then added to

Trace Determination of Zinc in Natural Water and Human Blood by Voltammetry

RAJENDRA P. NAMDEO and K. S. PITRE*

Department of Chemistry,
Dr. Hari Singh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 5 July 1990, revised 24 January 1991,
accepted 28 March 1991

VOLTAMMETRIC technique has not been extensively used for zinc determination¹. In the present study differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry (DPASV) has been employed for the determination of zinc(II) in natural water and human blood.

Experimental

Standard solution of zinc (0.1 M) was prepared and standardised². Polarographic recordings were performed on an Elico CL-90 pulse polarograph attached with a X-Y Polarocord LR-108. The polarographic cell consisted of three electrode assembly, glassy carbon fibre electrode as a working electrode, saturated calomel electrode as a reference

TABLE 1—CONCENTRATION OF Zn^{II} IN NATURAL WATER

Sample location	No. of assay	Volume of aliquots ml	DPASV Zn μg	SD	AAS Zn μg	SD
Surface level	20	5.0	—	—	—	—
	20	10.0	—	—	—	—
	20	20.0	—	—	—	—
Middle level	16	5.0	4.6	0.068	—	—
	16	10.0	8.9	0.072	8.8	0.76
	16	20.0	18.2	0.066	18.0	0.83
Bottom level	25	5.0	5.1	0.065	—	—
	25	10.0	10.4	0.070	9.8	0.70
	25	20.0	20.0	0.074	19.6	0.79

a mixture of concentrated H₂SO₄ (4.0 ml), HClO₄ (2 ml) and concentrated HNO₃ (4.0 ml) and refluxed for 3–4 h till colourless solution was obtained. The solution was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in distilled water and used for analysis (Table 2).

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Zn^{II} IN BLOOD

Blood collected from	No. of sample analysed	Zinc found			
		DPASV Zn $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	SD	AAS Zn $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	SD
Healthy individuals	25	0.90	0.06	0.92	0.42
Hypertension patients	20	1.05	0.08	1.04	0.46

The accuracy of the differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry has been verified by atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS). A perusal of data showed that DPASV technique is sensitive, accurate and precise.

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly thankful to Prof. S. P. Banerjee, Dean, Faculty of Science and Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. Hari Singh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, for facilities.

References

1. R. C. KAPOOR, J. KISHAN, K. C. K. MATHUR, P. SHARMA and M. MATHUR, "Trace Analysis and Technology Development", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1981; S. J. REDDY, P. VALENTA, H. W. NURNBERG and Z. FRESSENIUS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1982, **313**, 390; T. S. HARRISON, "Advances in Polarography", Symposium Publication Division, Pergamon, New York, 1960.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th ed., ELBS, London, 1978, p. 477.
3. R. G. DHANESHWAR and L. R. ZARAFAR, *Analyst*, 1980, **105**, 386.